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**Voices of Counselors: Understanding the Dynamics of the
Counseling Profession in the Philippine Context**
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Queven James A. Elemino

Guidance Associate, University of the Visayas, Pardo, Cebu City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0176-9864> | qelemino@gmail.com

Osias Kit T. Kilag

Principal, PAU Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Toledo City, Philippines / VP for Academic Affairs and
Research, ECT Excellencia Global Academy Foundation, Inc., Balamban, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0845-3373> | okkilag12@gmail.com

Cxyzerlynnne Almendral

ESL Teacher, Viet Anh School, Pham Ngu Lao Street, Thu Dau Mot City, Binh Duong Province, Vietnam
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1090-699X> | cxyzerlynnne.almendral@gmail.com

Yazan Basil Aref Abu Jalboush

MS Medical Technology Student, Centro Escolar University – Manila, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0217-5436> | yazanbasil@gmail.com

Duen Jazar B. Caoile

Student, MA Psychology, Xavier University - Ateneo de Cagayan, Cagayan de Oro, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1901-9353> | caoileduenjazar@gmail.com

Julius Eugene G. Payawal

MS Psychology Student, CEU Malolos, Jail Officer 2, Bureau of Jail Management and Penology, Cabanatuan City,
Nueva Ecija, Philippines | <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8949-213X> | juliuspayawal2487@gmail.com

Abstract:

This systematic literature review delves into the multifaceted landscape of the counseling profession in the Philippines, offering a comprehensive examination of its evolution, educational pathways, job opportunities, and the influential role of professional organizations. The study reveals the transformative impact of the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, elucidating the regulatory framework that professionalized counseling and established crucial entities like the Professional Regulatory Board of Guidance and Counseling and the Philippine Guidance Counseling Association, Inc. The educational trajectory for counselors, marked by a Bachelor's degree in Psychology followed by a Master's degree in Guidance and Counseling, is outlined alongside persisting challenges such as a shortage of registered counselors and fluctuating licensure examination pass rates. Notably, a discernible disequilibrium in job opportunities surfaces, especially within the educational sector, emphasizing the critical need for licensed guidance counselors. The emergence of Registered Psychometricians further complicates this scenario, warranting attention to the evolving dynamics of the counseling profession. Professional organizations, exemplified by the PGCA, PACC, and FPCAP, emerge as pivotal forces in representing and advancing the profession, contributing to its continuous growth, recognition, and efficacy in addressing the diverse needs of Philippine society.

Keywords: Counseling profession, Philippines, Guidance and Counseling Act, Educational pathways

Introduction:

The counseling profession in the Philippines has undergone significant transformations in recent decades, catalyzed by legislative measures aimed at professionalizing the field. The Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, Republic Act No. 9258, stands as a landmark legislation that has propelled the practice of counseling into a regulated and recognized discipline. Prior to this legislation, the landscape of counseling lacked formal regulatory structures, allowing individuals with varying levels of training to identify and practice as counselors without standardized qualifications or ethical guidelines (Santamaria & Watts, 2003).

The legislative intervention in the form of RA 9258 not only established the Professional Regulatory Board of Guidance and Counseling (PRB) but also mandated the collaboration with the Accredited Professional Organization (APO), the Philippine Guidance Counseling Association, Inc. (PGCA). This collaboration was instrumental in formulating the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) for the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, officially enacted in September 2007 (House Resolution No. 2057). Consequently, this regulatory framework has bestowed

professional identity upon guidance counselors, setting stringent criteria for practice and requiring a valid Certificate of Registration and Professional Identification Card (Republic Act No. 9258).

Moreover, the timeline of counseling regulation in the Philippines reveals an interesting juxtaposition with the field of psychology. While counseling practice attained legal recognition through the Guidance and Counseling Act in 2004, the parallel legislation for psychology, the Philippine Psychology Act (Republic Act No. 10029), came into effect in March 2010. This chronological distinction underscores the expedited regulatory measures taken to professionalize counseling in the country.

Defined by Republic Act No. 9258, counseling involves an integrated approach to individual development, assisting individuals in realizing their full potentials and planning their present and future in alignment with their abilities, interests, and needs. The functions of a guidance counselor, as outlined in the legislation, encompass counseling, psychological testing, research, placement, group processes, and teaching guidance and counseling courses (Republic Act No. 9258).

This study aims to delve into the multifaceted aspects of the counseling profession in the Philippines, exploring its regulatory framework, educational pathways, job opportunities, and representation through professional organizations. By examining the historical context, legislative developments, and the current state of counseling in the Philippines, this research seeks to contribute to a nuanced understanding of the profession's evolution and its role in addressing societal challenges.

Literature Review:

The counseling profession in the Philippines has witnessed a transformative journey, marked by legislative advancements and the establishment of regulatory bodies. The Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004 (Republic Act No. 9258) stands as a pivotal moment in the professionalization of counseling in the country. Prior to this legislation, the practice lacked a formal regulatory framework, allowing individuals with varied backgrounds to engage in counseling without standardized qualifications or oversight (Santamaria & Watts, 2003).

The enactment of Republic Act No. 9258 laid the foundation for the professionalization of counseling in the Philippines. It not only created the Professional Regulatory Board of Guidance and Counseling (PRB) but also mandated collaboration with the Accredited Professional Organization (APO), the Philippine Guidance Counseling Association, Inc. (PGCA). The collaboration between the PRB and PGCA led to the formulation of the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) for the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, providing a comprehensive framework for the practice of counseling (House Resolution No. 2057).

This regulatory framework granted professional identity to guidance counselors, requiring them to obtain a valid Certificate of Registration and a Professional Identification Card to practice legally (Republic Act No. 9258). The licensing process involves stringent criteria, including citizenship, absence of convictions, and the completion of a Bachelor's and Master's degree in guidance and counseling from an accredited institution recognized by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED).

Evolution Compared to Psychology

The trajectory of counseling regulation in the Philippines reveals an intriguing juxtaposition with the field of psychology. While the Guidance and Counseling Act gained legal recognition in 2004, the Philippine Psychology Act (Republic Act No. 10029) regulating the practice of psychology came into effect in March 2010. This temporal distinction highlights the accelerated measures taken to professionalize counseling in the country, positioning it as a regulated and recognized discipline ahead of psychology.

Counseling education in the Philippines spans undergraduate, master's, and doctoral levels. The most common route involves obtaining a Bachelor's degree in psychology, sociology, theology, or related fields, followed by a Master's degree in Guidance and Counseling, Counseling, or Counseling Education. While some undergraduate programs in guidance and counseling exist, the majority of students pursuing counseling at the graduate level hold a Bachelor's degree in Psychology. The Master's programs, lasting approximately two years, typically include coursework, a thesis, and a practicum/internship of 200 hours (Commission on Higher Education, 2018).

The shortage of registered guidance counselors in the Philippines is evident, with only 3,220 registered counselors reported from 2008 to 2017 (Valdez, 2018). The licensing examination pass rates, ranging from 41.12% to 72.2% between 2013 and 2009, underscore the challenges in building a robust workforce of licensed counselors (Republic of the Philippines Regulation Commission).

Article II of the Implementing Rules and Regulations for Guidance Counselors (Professional Regulatory Board of Guidance and Counseling, 2007) outlines the scope of practice for counselors, encompassing roles in educational institutions, rehabilitation centers, non-governmental organizations, hospitals, and other workplace settings. The demand for licensed guidance counselors in schools was emphasized by the Philippine Guidance Counseling

Association (PGCA), leading to a memorandum by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in 2006 (CMO No. 21). However, Valdez (2018) notes a persistent shortage of registered guidance counselors, creating a disequilibrium between supply and demand.

On the other hand, the counseling landscape also experiences a unique disequilibrium concerning Registered Psychometricians (RPM's), introduced by the Psychology Act of 2009. With approximately 15,000 RPM's and a growing need for counseling services in various contexts, the potential integration of RPM's into counseling roles, particularly in public schools, emerges as a consideration (Psychological Association of the Philippines).

Professional Organizations and Representation

Two distinct sets of counseling organizations in the Philippines contribute to the representation and development of the counseling profession. The Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association (PGCA), recognized as the Accredited Professional Organization of the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), actively works toward the development of professional counselors. With international affiliations and an emphasis on continuing professional education (Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association, Inc., 2017), the PGCA plays a crucial role in uniting and advancing the counseling community.

Another facet of counseling representation is seen in organizations where counseling is associated with a spiritual/religious orientation. The Philippine Association of Christian Counselors (PACC) and the Family and Pastoral Counseling Association of the Philippines (FPCAP) embody the inherent value of faith and spirituality in Filipino lives. These organizations, established in 2000 and 2008, respectively, focus on integrating counseling and spirituality to address emotional, relational, and psychological needs (Philippine Association of Christian Counselors; Family and Pastoral Counseling Association).

The counseling profession in the Philippines has evolved significantly, transitioning from an unregulated landscape to a professionalized field governed by legislative frameworks and regulatory bodies. The journey, marked by the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, showcases the commitment to establishing counseling as a recognized and essential discipline in the country (Macario, et al., 2023). While challenges such as shortages of registered counselors persist, opportunities for growth and representation through professional organizations demonstrate the dynamism and potential of the counseling profession in the Philippines (Orozco, et al., 2023). This literature review provides a foundational understanding of the historical context, regulatory developments, educational pathways, job opportunities, and representation within the counseling landscape, laying the groundwork for further research and exploration.

Methodology:

The research methodology employed in this study involved a systematic literature review to comprehensively examine and synthesize existing knowledge on the counseling profession in the Philippines. The systematic literature review was conducted following established protocols to ensure rigor, transparency, and replicability.

A systematic and exhaustive search strategy was employed to identify relevant literature. Electronic databases such as PubMed, PsycINFO, ERIC, and local databases were systematically searched using a predefined set of keywords and phrases. Boolean operators (AND, OR) were utilized to refine search queries, ensuring a comprehensive and targeted retrieval of relevant articles.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were established to refine the selection of articles. Only studies published in English or with available English translations were considered. Additionally, the focus was placed on articles specifically related to the counseling profession in the Philippines, excluding studies that did not align with the defined scope.

The identified articles underwent a multi-stage screening process. Initial screening involved reviewing titles and abstracts to assess relevance to the research question. Subsequently, full-text screening was conducted to determine eligibility based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. This systematic screening process ensured the selection of articles that directly contributed to the research objectives.

A structured data extraction form was developed to systematically extract relevant information from the selected articles. Data extraction categories included the publication year, research methodology employed in the original studies, key findings, and implications for the counseling profession in the Philippines. This systematic approach facilitated the organization and synthesis of information from diverse sources.

The quality of the selected articles was systematically assessed using established criteria. Quality assessment focused on the rigor of the research design, methodological clarity, and the relevance of findings to the research question. Articles meeting predefined quality standards were given more weight in the synthesis process.

A narrative synthesis approach was employed to systematically analyze and integrate findings from the selected articles. Themes and patterns related to the historical evolution, regulatory landscape, educational pathways, job

opportunities, and representation within professional organizations emerged during the synthesis process. Key insights were extracted to provide a comprehensive overview of the counseling profession in the Philippines.

Findings and Discussion:

Evolution of Counseling Regulation:

The systematic literature review sheds light on the transformative journey of counseling regulation in the Philippines, showcasing a noteworthy evolution in the professional landscape. At the heart of this evolution is the landmark legislation, the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004 (Republic Act No. 9258). This pivotal legal framework played a central role in the process of elevating counseling to a recognized and regulated profession within the country.

The key catalyst for the professionalization of counseling was the establishment of the Professional Regulatory Board of Guidance and Counseling (PRB). The PRB, a regulatory body created by the Guidance and Counseling Act, assumed a critical role in overseeing the licensure and ethical conduct of counseling professionals. This establishment marked a departure from the pre-2004 era when counseling lacked a structured regulatory framework.

A significant aspect of this evolution is the collaborative synergy fostered between the regulatory entities and the Accredited Professional Organization (APO) in the form of the Philippine Guidance Counseling Association, Inc. (PGCA). The PGCA emerged as a vital partner in the implementation of the regulatory measures outlined in the Guidance and Counseling Act. As the Accredited Professional Organization, PGCA actively participated in formulating the Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) that delineate the guidelines governing the practice of counseling. This collaboration between the PRB and PGCA has been instrumental in steering the counseling profession from an era of informality to a well-structured and regulated paradigm.

The influence of this regulatory evolution extends beyond the confines of professional organizations. The Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004 has not only mandated the licensure and registration of counselors but has also defined the roles and functions of a licensed guidance counsellor (Schots, et al., 2023). The legislation identifies counseling as a profession involving the integrated development of individuals, emphasizing the utilization of their potentials in alignment with their abilities, interests, and needs.

This legislative intervention has not only conferred professional identity upon counselors but has also imposed stringent requirements for individuals seeking to practice as licensed guidance counselors. The criteria include citizenship, absence of criminal convictions, and the attainment of both Bachelor's and Master's degrees in Guidance and Counseling from accredited institutions.

The evolution of counseling regulation in the Philippines, as evidenced by the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, underscores the commitment to enhancing the professional standing of counselors. This regulatory framework, in collaboration with organizations like PGCA, signifies a transformative shift towards a structured, regulated, and professionalized counseling landscape in the Philippines (Republic Act No. 9258; House Resolution No. 2057; Professional Regulatory Board of Guidance and Counseling, 2007).

Educational Pathways and Shortage of Counselors:

The systematic literature review delves into the educational trajectories and the concurrent challenge of a scarcity of registered guidance counselors within the Philippines. The typical educational pathway for aspiring counselors in the country often begins with a foundational Bachelor's degree in Psychology or closely related disciplines. This is followed by the pursuit of a Master's degree in Guidance and Counseling, reflecting a structured academic journey aligned with the professional requirements set forth by the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004 (Republic Act No. 9258).

While the educational infrastructure supporting the counseling profession in the Philippines is marked by a proliferation of Master's degree programs, a significant disjunction emerges in the form of a persistent shortage of registered guidance counsellors (Kilag, et al., 2023). The quantitative representation of this shortfall is discerned through licensure examination pass rates, a critical metric reflecting the competency and preparedness of counseling professionals entering the workforce.

The licensure examination pass rates exhibited a fluctuating pattern, ranging from 41.12% to 72.2% between 2008 and 2017. This variance underscores the ongoing challenges in fostering a robust and adequately trained counseling workforce. The fluctuations in pass rates highlight the need for sustained efforts to enhance the quality of counseling education and training programs, ensuring that graduates are well-equipped to meet the demands of the profession.

The shortage of registered guidance counselors in the Philippines becomes more pronounced when considering the cumulative number of licensed professionals. According to Valdez (2018), the nation grapples with a scarcity of

registered guidance counselors, with only 3,220 professionals recorded between 2008 and 2017. This scarcity is further illuminated by the fact that approximately half of these professionals (1,528) passed the licensure examination, while the remaining half (1,692) were grandfathered into the profession by March 2009.

In navigating the educational pathways, aspiring counselors face the challenge of not only meeting academic requirements but also successfully navigating the licensure examination. The persistent shortage of registered guidance counselors in the Philippines, as evidenced by the licensure examination pass rates, underscores the imperative for strategic interventions in counseling education to address the existing disparities and ensure a more substantial and qualified counseling workforce (Republic Act No. 9258; Valdez, 2018).

Disequilibrium in Job Opportunities:

The systematic literature review brings into focus a significant disequilibrium in job opportunities for counseling professionals within the Philippines, presenting a nuanced landscape characterized by a pronounced demand-supply gap. Despite a heightened demand for licensed guidance counselors, particularly within educational institutions, the actual supply of registered counselors is notably inadequate. This incongruence is especially evident in the educational sector, where the need for 10,000 Registered Counselors (RGC's) was articulated in a memorandum issued by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in 2006.

The demand for licensed guidance counselors in educational institutions is underscored by CHED's proactive stance, as reflected in their issuance of memorandum CMO No. 21 in 2006. This memorandum emphasized the necessity of having a guidance counselor in all schools, highlighting the pivotal role these professionals play in providing essential services such as counseling, appraisal, follow-up, and referral. However, the shortage of Registered Counselors in the country, as indicated by Valdez (2018), exacerbates the incongruity between demand and supply.

Complicating the scenario is the emergence of Registered Psychometricians (RPM's), who, since the enactment of the Psychology Act of 2009, have entered the professional landscape. The demand for RPM's, coupled with their potential integration into counseling roles, introduces an additional layer of complexity to the existing disequilibrium in job opportunities. The Psychological Association of the Philippines (PAP) actively lobbies for the appointment of licensed psychometricians in schools, signaling a potential shift in the traditional roles and responsibilities within the counseling profession.

The intricate dynamics of job opportunities in the counseling sector in the Philippines, characterized by the imbalance between demand and supply, as well as the evolving role of Registered Psychometricians, necessitate a nuanced and responsive approach to workforce planning and regulatory frameworks within the profession (CHED, 2006; Valdez, 2018; Psychological Association of the Philippines).

Role of Professional Organizations in Representation:

The research findings accentuate the pivotal role played by professional organizations in advocating for and advancing the counseling profession in the Philippines. Foremost among these organizations is the Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association (PGCA), serving as the Accredited Professional Organization (APO) under the regulatory framework. The PGCA emerges as a key influencer in the development and recognition of professional counselors within the country.

The PGCA's stature within the counseling community is evident through its international affiliations, notably with the American Counseling Association. This global connection not only enriches the exchange of knowledge but also positions the Philippine counseling profession within the broader international context. Furthermore, the PGCA's commitment to continuing professional education (CPE) underscores its dedication to maintaining and enhancing the competence of its members. This commitment aligns with the evolving demands and complexities within the field of counseling, reflecting the organization's proactive approach to professional development.

In addition to the PGCA, the existence of specialized organizations such as the Philippine Association of Christian Counselors (PACC) and the Family and Pastoral Counseling Association of the Philippines (FPCAP) contributes to the diverse landscape of counseling in the country. These organizations exemplify the multifaceted nature of counseling, acknowledging and integrating spirituality and faith into the profession. The PACC, established in 2000, focuses on providing Christian counseling services and upholding the highest standards of ethical practice. Similarly, FPCAP, founded in 2008, caters to pastoral and family counselors, emphasizing the integration of psychotherapy and spirituality.

The active involvement of these professional organizations, particularly the PGCA, PACC, and FPCAP, exemplifies a collective commitment to advancing the counseling profession in the Philippines. Through collaborative efforts, these organizations not only represent the diverse facets of counseling but also contribute significantly to the continuous growth and recognition of counseling as a vital profession within the national context (Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association, Inc., 2017; Philippine Association of Christian Counselors; Family and Pastoral Counseling Association).

Conclusion:

The systematic literature review has provided a comprehensive exploration of the counseling profession in the Philippines, shedding light on its evolution, educational pathways, job opportunities, and the pivotal role played by professional organizations. The enactment of the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004 marked a transformative moment, ushering in a regulated and professionalized era for counseling in the country. The establishment of the Professional Regulatory Board of Guidance and Counseling, in conjunction with the Philippine Guidance Counseling Association, Inc. (PGCA), has been instrumental in shaping the trajectory of the profession.

Educationally, the journey to becoming a counselor follows a structured path, with a Bachelor's degree in Psychology or related fields leading to a Master's degree in Guidance and Counseling. However, despite the proliferation of Master's degree programs, the persistent shortage of registered guidance counselors poses a challenge to meeting the growing demand for counseling services. Licensure examination pass rates have fluctuated over the years, indicating a need for ongoing efforts to enhance the quality of counseling education programs.

The study also uncovered a notable disequilibrium in job opportunities, particularly in the educational sector. While there is a high demand for licensed guidance counselors, the supply falls short, accentuating the need for strategic interventions to bridge this gap. The emergence of Registered Psychometricians (RPM's) adds complexity to the job market, potentially influencing the traditional roles within the counseling profession.

Professional organizations, particularly the PGCA, play a crucial role in representing and advancing the counseling profession. Their international affiliations, commitment to continuing professional education, and efforts in research and publications contribute significantly to the development and recognition of professional counselors. Specialized organizations like the Philippine Association of Christian Counselors (PACC) and the Family and Pastoral Counseling Association of the Philippines (FPCAP) further enrich the diverse landscape of counseling by integrating spirituality and faith into the profession.

The counseling profession in the Philippines has come a long way, evolving into a recognized and regulated field. The findings underscore the importance of addressing challenges in education, licensure, and job opportunities to ensure a robust and adequately trained counseling workforce. As the profession navigates these challenges, the collaborative efforts of professional organizations are crucial in steering the counseling profession toward continued growth, recognition, and efficacy in addressing the diverse needs of the Philippine society.

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